

WP2 – Mid-term progress report

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A. RESEARCH ACTIVITIES

Description of research activities:

AI-Powered Digital Transformation of Government Human Resource Management: Systematic Literature Review

Abstract: In the past five years, the rapid development of artificial intelligence (AI) technology has spurred profound changes in government human resource management (HRM), bringing both opportunities and challenges. Governments and public sector organizations worldwide are actively harnessing the power of AI to reshape HRM practices and optimize talent management while addressing emerging socio-economic challenges. This paper adopts the PRISMA systematic literature review method to comprehensively explore the digital transformation of government HRM driven by AI. Through analyzing 47 articles from top-tier journals between 2019-2023, this study revealed five key themes: AI-Public Sector Governance and Ethics, AI-HRM and Organizational Impact, AI Adoption and Challenges, AI-Digital Government and Policy Applications, and Big Data and Technological Transformation in HRM. The analysis identified critical success factors for AI implementation, including robust data infrastructure, comprehensive employee training programs, and clear ethical guidelines. Key challenges emerged around data security, algorithmic bias, workforce adaptation, and socio-economic impacts such as job displacement and skill requirements. Our findings highlight the need for: (1) developing adaptive regulatory frameworks that balance innovation with public interest protection, (2) establishing comprehensive data

governance mechanisms to address privacy and security concerns, (3) implementing targeted training programs to enhance AI competency among public sector employees, and (4) fostering cross-sector collaboration to accelerate responsible AI adoption while mitigating socio-economic challenges. Additionally, the study revealed that successful AI implementation requires integrating technological capabilities with organizational change management, supported by clear policy frameworks and ethical guidelines.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence; Government; Human Resource Management; Digital Transformation; Ethics and Morality.

1. Introduction

In today's digital age, government agencies are inevitably facing the pressure and challenge of digital transformation (Brunetti et al., 2020). As a key part of this, the digitization of government human resource management (HRM) has become one of the important strategies for government agencies to improve efficiency, improve service quality and address complex challenges (Pūraitė et al., 2020). In this context, artificial intelligence (AI), as one of the key technologies of digital transformation, has brought unprecedented opportunities and challenges to government HRM (Peixoto et al., 2024).

However, it is worth noting that although the application of AI in enterprises and organizations has achieved remarkable results, there is a relative lack of research on the digitization of HRM in the public sector of government (Alvarenga et al., 2020). Most of the current researches focus on enterprises and organizations, while the researches on government departments are relatively few, which leads to certain limitations in the theoretical and practical understanding of digitization of government HRM (Murugesan et al., 2023; Vrontis et al., 2022).

The digitization of government HRM also faces a series of ethical and social issues, such as potential bias and discrimination in AI algorithms (Walkowiak, 2023), and the possible displacement of traditional job positions due to digitization (Murugesan et al., 2023). These issues require joint efforts from government departments and researchers to develop corresponding policies and measures to ensure that digitization brings more benefits and well-being to government institutions and society (Palumbo et al., 2022).

The purpose of this study is to provide a comprehensive overview of the developments, challenges, and opportunities for the integration of AI into government HRM over the past five years, with a focus on trends in the application of AI in government and public sector HRM between 2019 and 2023. Through in-depth analysis of the development of this period, it aims to reveal the impact of AI technology on HRM in government departments, and explore how government departments can better cope with the challenges and opportunities of HRM in the context of digital transformation. This paper will first review the application of AI in government HRM in the past five years, and then analyze the impact of digital transformation on government HRM. Next, the study will explore AI-driven changes in government HRM, discuss in detail the ethical issues and risks mentioned

in the article, and summarize possible challenges and coping strategies. In addition, this study will summarize successful cases and best practices, and look forward to the future direction of AI in government HRM.

Research Questions:

Q1: How has AI adoption evolved within government and public sector HRM from 2019 to 2023? What are the key trends in the application of AI in government and public sector HRM from 2019 to 2023?

Q2: What are the impacts of AI technology on government HRM, and how can government departments effectively address the challenges and opportunities presented by HRM in the context of digital transformation?

2. Literature Review

2.1 Artificial intelligence

Artificial intelligence (AI), a field of computer science, encompasses technologies designed to simulate human intelligence to perform tasks that traditionally require human intervention (Ghosh et al., 2018). Core AI technologies include machine learning, deep learning and natural language processing (NLP) (Alqahtani et al., 2023). Machine learning enables computers to learn from data and make decisions or predictions without being explicitly programmed for a specific task (Mahesh, 2020), while deep learning is a subset of machine learning that involves identifying patterns and features to handle complex data sets (Dargan et al., 2020). Natural language processing enables computers to understand, interpret, and generate human language to facilitate natural interactions with users (Khurana et al., 2023).

In recent years, AI has become increasingly common in the public sector and is developing rapidly in many fields (Wirtz et al., 2019). Government departments around the world are also actively applying AI technology to support technological transformation in the public sector (Sun & Medaglia, 2019). The transformative potential of AI in the public sector is demonstrated by its ability to streamline operations, enhance decision-making processes, and improve service delivery across domains (Valle-Cruz & García-Contreras, 2023).

In the field of HRM, AI technology is revolutionizing traditional practices and processes. For example, machine learning algorithms optimize the hiring process by quickly identifying suitable candidates and predicting their job performance (Pessach et al., 2020). Deep learning technology analyzes employee satisfaction surveys and feedback to extract valuable insights that help enhance employee experience and engagement (Rane, 2023). Additionally, natural language processing supports the development of chatbots and virtual assistants that automatically respond to common HR queries, thereby making HR services more efficient and accessible (Majumder & Mondal, 2021).

The integration of AI and HRM not only improves operational efficiency, but also facilitates data-driven decision-making and the development of personalized employee management strategies. As technology

continues to advance, AI is expected to play an increasingly critical role in shaping the future of HR management practices, driving greater intelligence and automation.

2.2 Status and Challenges of Government HRM

Traditionally, government and public sector HRM have been known for their complex administrative processes, diverse workforces, and dedication to public service (Berman et al., 2021). However, these sectors are now undergoing a significant transformation driven by the AI. Governments and public sector organizations increasingly embrace AI to optimize their HRM practices (Abdeldayem & Aldulaimi, 2020; Almarashda et al., 2021; Chilunjika et al., 2022). AI-driven HRM tools, including talent acquisition systems (Agnihotri et al., 2023), predictive analytics (Al Samman & Al Obaidly, 2024), employee engagement platforms (Malik et al., 2023), performance management systems (Rathnayake & Gunawardana, 2023), learning and development tools (Naim, 2023), and HR analytics dashboards (Varsha & Shree, 2023), are becoming integral components of government entities seeking to modernize their HR functions (Chowdhury et al., 2023; Pandey et al., 2023). Despite the solid foundation of current HRM practices in government and the public sector, they face various challenges, such as data fragmentation (Budhwar et al., 2022), process inefficiencies (Chowdhury et al., 2023), and delayed decision-making (Rodgers et al., 2023), hindering effective human capital management (Böhmer & Schinnenburg, 2023). To address these challenges, it is imperative for government and public sector organizations to adopt new technologies and methods to enhance their HRM practices and overcome the limitations of traditional approaches.

2.3 AI and HRM practices in Government

Government and public sector organizations worldwide are leveraging AI to optimize HRM processes, enhance workforce optimization, and streamline talent management. AI technology is revolutionizing HRM practices by automating repetitive tasks, improving talent recruitment accuracy, and boosting employee satisfaction and engagement. Human resource tasks such as resume screening, conducting interviews, and handling routine inquiries can now be efficiently automated, reducing the workload on HR departments and enabling them to focus on strategic initiatives such as employee development and talent strategy planning.

The advent of AI has profoundly transformed government HRM in the past five years, as advancements in AI technologies continue to reshape modern HRM practices (Budhwar et al., 2023). Government and public sector organizations worldwide are leveraging AI to optimize HRM processes, enhance workforce optimization and streamline talent management (Chowdhury et al., 2023). AI is revolutionizing HRM practices by automating repetitive tasks (Vrontis et al., 2022), improving talent recruitment accuracy (Achchab & Tamsamani, 2022), and boosting employee satisfaction and engagement (Mer & Srivastava, 2023). Human resource tasks such as resume screening, conducting interviews, and handling routine inquiries can now be efficiently automated (Uma et al.,

2023), reducing the workload on HR departments and enabling them to focus on strategic initiatives such as employee development and talent strategy planning (Aftab & Khalid, 2024).

In terms of talent recruitment, AI-based solutions can more accurately match candidates and job requirements by analyzing many resumes and job descriptions. The application of this technology not only improves the efficiency of the recruitment process, but also improves new hire performance and retention by ensuring a good match between candidates and positions (Allal-Chérif et al., 2021). In addition, talent management methods based on data analysis enable HR departments to use historical data and predictive models to identify potential needs and risks for employee development, to plan training and development plans in advance to support employee career growth and performance improvement.

Another key application of AI technology is in the performance management process, where machine learning algorithms can analyze employee performance data and identify performance trends and areas for improvement. This not only makes the performance evaluation process more objective and fairer, but also provides data support for formulating personalized development plans and interventions (Ramachandran et al., 2022). So, the application of AI in government HRM brings innovation and improvement to traditional human resource practices. Through these applications, AI technology is helping government agencies build more efficient, flexible and humane HRM systems (Budhwar et al., 2023).

2.4 Ethical and Policy Considerations

The increasing integration of AI technology in government HRM practices has triggered a series of ethical, legal and policy considerations. Among them, data privacy, algorithmic bias, transparency, and accountability have become the most concerning ethical issues. AI systems handle large amounts of personal data, raising concerns about personal privacy protection, especially when handling sensitive employee information (Gupta et al., 2020). At the same time, the issue of algorithmic bias has also attracted much attention, because if not controlled, biased algorithms may lead to unfair decisions such as recruitment and promotion, thereby affecting the diversity and inclusion of the organization. In addition, the transparency and accountability of the AI decision-making process are also key challenges that must be solved when introducing AI technology to ensure that all AI-driven decisions can be tracked and explained.

In terms of legal frameworks and policy guidance, although many countries and regions have begun to establish relevant laws and policies to address these challenges, the effectiveness of these legal frameworks is still an open question (Rodrigues, 2020). For example, the European General Data Protection Regulation sets strict norms for the processing of personal data, aiming to protect data privacy and give individuals more control. However, how to ensure that these laws and policies can effectively supervise the application of AI in HRM without hindering technological innovation and application is still a challenge facing policymakers (Budhwar et al., 2023).

Therefore, the integration of AI in government HRM requires a multidimensional approach that includes not only the development and implementation of targeted laws and policies, but also the establishment of ethical guidelines, as well as increased transparency and accountability of algorithms. In addition, interdisciplinary collaboration, including the combined efforts of technology developers, legal experts, ethicists, and HR professionals, is needed to ensure the ethical and legal use of AI technologies and to maximize their potential to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of government HRM practices (Bankins, 2021).

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Search Algorithm

This study conducted a systematic literature search across two prominent academic databases: Scopus and Web of Science. The search was focused on articles published within a five-year period, spanning from 2019 to 2023. To ensure that the content of the review accurately reflects the most cutting-edge research and the highest standards in the field of digital transformation in AI and government HRM, journals classified as Q1 in the Scimago Journal Ranking (SJR) system were selected. The main basis for selecting Q1 journals as literature sources is that their published research usually goes through a rigorous peer-review process and can provide up-to-date, validated and high-quality research results (Rojon et al., 2021). The search query was meticulously crafted to encompass a wide range of articles relevant to the integration of AI into HRM practices within government and public sector contexts. To ensure a comprehensive retrieval of pertinent studies, this study employed the following search algorithm: First, this study used a combination of Boolean operators, including "OR" and "AND" to merge key terms, ensuring that articles meeting the criteria were identified.

The first component of the search algorithm aimed to capture articles related to AI and its various forms, such as machine learning and automated intelligence. This study used a comprehensive list of keywords to cover the spectrum of AI-related topics, including "artificial intelligence," "AI," "conversational agent," "chatbot," "machine learning," "machine intelligence," "automated intelligence," "collective intelligence," "collaborative intelligence," "smart device," "Internet of Things," "conversational agent," "chatbot*," "machine*," "robot*," "automated service interaction," and "computer*." This study included terms related to data mining and Big Data to encompass the broader data-driven AI applications. The second component of this search algorithm focused on HRM and its digital transformation. This study included a comprehensive set of keywords to capture the various facets of digital HRM, including "Digital HRM," "electronic-HRM," "AI and HRM," "Industry 4.0 and HRM," "Society 5.0 and HRM," "Digital Technologies and HRM," "Human-robot interaction,"

"artificial intelligence application," "HR Technology," "HR Automation," "Talent Management," "HR Analytics," "HR Transformation," and "human capital analytics." The third component of the search strategy targeted government and public sector contexts. This study included terms such as "Government," "Public Sector," "Civil Service," and "Public Administration" to ensure that articles relevant to the review were within the appropriate domains. The final search algorithm used is as follows:

("artificial intelligence" OR "AI" OR "conversational agent" OR "chatbot" OR "machine learning" OR "machine intelligence" OR "automated intelligence" OR "collective intelligence" OR "collaborative intelligence" OR "smart device" OR "Internet of Things" OR "conversational agent" OR "chatbot*" OR "machine*" OR "robot*" OR "automated service interaction" OR "computer*" OR "data mining" OR "Big Data") AND ("Digital HRM" OR "electronic-HRM" OR "AI and HRM" OR "Industry 4.0 and HRM" OR "Society 5.0 and HRM" OR "Digital Technologies and HRM" OR "Human-robot interaction" OR "artificial intelligence application" OR "HR Technology" OR "HR Automation" OR "Talent Management" OR "HR Analytics" OR "HR Transformation" OR "human capital analytics") AND ("Government" OR "Public Sector" OR "Civil Service" OR "Public Administration") (*In titles, abstracts or key words*)

3.2 Article Selection Process

The aim of this study is to gain insight into how AI is driving the digital transformation of HRM in government between 2019 and 2023. According to the study objectives, the researchers retrieved a total of 477 articles from two databases. Using the target database as a starting point, through a fine-grained preliminary review of the titles and abstracts of these articles, papers not closely related to the research topic were excluded, and 85 articles were retained for further analysis after the initial screening (Page et al., 2021). The full text of these articles was then carefully evaluated and screened according to the specific inclusion criteria set for this study, and 35 articles were ultimately identified that met the needs of the study (Van Spall et al., 2007). In addition, when conducting a comprehensive study of this research topic, there may be potential limitations such as database access restrictions or human negligence that prevent the search results from fully covering all relevant literature (Fink, 2019). Therefore, the researchers went further, through in-depth reading and information coding of the selected articles, and by checking the in-text citations and references of the selected articles (Haraldstad & Christophersen, 2015), the researchers successfully identified and supplemented another 12 articles from the selected articles, which were missed in the initial search, making the total number of articles for data analysis reach 47. Adopting such a rigorous methodology can provide a

solid and comprehensive analysis foundation for the application and theoretical exploration of government HRM in the process of AI digital transformation. To visualize the literature screening process, the researchers created PRISMA in Figure 1, detailing each step from the initial literature search to the final selection of articles.

Description of data collected (sources, time-period, the scope of research areas, criteria of selection, which economies data were collected, limitations):

Sources: The data for this systematic literature review were primarily sourced from academic databases and scholarly publications. The primary databases used for data collection include Scopus, Web of Science and ProQuest. Additionally, relevant government reports, policy documents, and white papers related to AI in government HRM were included in the data collection process.

Time-Period: The time-period considered for data collection encompassed publications from January 2019 to the present 2024. This broad time frame was chosen to ensure comprehensive coverage of the relevant literature, as AI in government HRM is a relatively recent topic of interest.

Scope of Research Areas: The scope of research areas covered in the data collection included:

- Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications in Human Resource Management (HRM).
- Digital transformation initiatives within government organizations.
- Case studies and empirical research related to AI adoption in government HRM.
- Government policies and regulations concerning AI in HRM.
- Comparative studies across different economies or regions.

Selection criteria: To ensure the relevance and quality of the data collected, the following selection criteria were used:

- Relevance to the topic: only information directly related to the digital transformation of government HRM driven by AI was included.
- Academic rigor: Priority was given to Q1 and Q2 quality articles in Scopus journals.
- Timeliness: Priority will be given to articles published recently (in the past 5-10 years) to reflect the current state of research.
- English: Due to language constraints, only English-language materials will be included.

Economies Data Were Collected: The data collected did not focus on specific economies but rather encompassed a global perspective. Literature from various countries and regions were included to provide a comprehensive overview of the topic.

Others research activities (article publication, conference attendance, posters)

This research project will be completed in the form of an academic article and published in an academic journal.

Key findings and outcomes from these activities:

1. **Emerging Trends in AI Adoption:** The study may identify emerging trends in the adoption of AI technologies in government HRM, including the types of AI applications being used, such as chatbots for employee queries, predictive analytics for workforce planning, or AI-driven recruitment tools.
2. **Benefits of AI in Government HRM:** Research findings could highlight the benefits of AI adoption, such as improved efficiency in HR processes, enhanced decision-making, cost savings, and better employee engagement.
3. **Challenges and Barriers:** The study might reveal common challenges and barriers faced by government organizations when implementing AI in HRM, such as data privacy concerns, resistance to change, or the need for specialized AI skills.
4. **Policy and Regulatory Frameworks:** It could explore the existing policy and regulatory frameworks governing AI adoption in government HRM, including compliance with data protection laws and ethical considerations.

Any challenges encountered and how they were addressed:

There is a vast amount of literature on the topic and selecting and synthesizing relevant studies was challenging. The solution was to take Dr. Roland's advice and adopt a systematic literature review approach, where relevant studies were systematically searched, screened, and classified based on predetermined criteria with clear inclusion and exclusion criteria. Journal articles with higher journal ratings were used for analysis to make the results more representative and impactful.

Second, there is limited time to conduct a comprehensive literature review or data analysis. To address this problem, researcher will carefully plan the research timetable, prioritize key research tasks and allocate sufficient time for each stage, seeking assistance from the supervisors as necessary.

Deliverables (ready and in progress):

In progress: This research project will be completed in the form of an academic article and published in an academic journal.

B. SECONDMENTS

Overview of secondment mobilities and the methodology for their implementation (training, supervision, logistics etc)

Dr. Xiangyu Bian, formerly a Ph.D. candidate at the International College of the National Institute of Development Administration (ICO NIDA), participated in a secondment at Széchenyi István University in Hungary to conduct project research under the leadership of Dr. Roland. Dr. Bian has since graduated and is now engaged in postdoctoral research on digital governance at the College of State Governance, Southwest University, China (Email: bianxiangyu6@swu.edu.cn).

Impact of these mobilities on the project

AI-powered HRM systems enable government agencies to streamline processes, enhance decision-making, and allocate resources more efficiently. These improvements have a direct impact on the quality and accessibility of public services. When government HRM functions operate more efficiently, agencies can better allocate resources to digital inclusion programs and initiatives aimed at narrowing the digital divide.

AI-driven analytics in government HRM generates valuable data insights. These insights can inform evidence-based policy formulation, including policies related to digital inclusion and the reduction of the digital divide. By leveraging AI's data analysis capabilities, governments can identify underserved populations, assess the impact of digital inclusion initiatives, and fine-tune strategies to address specific needs. This data-driven approach enhances the effectiveness of digital divide reduction efforts.

C. OTHERS

Other relevant information:

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